

Umarali Normatov and His Contribution to the Development of the University School of Literary Criticism in Uzbekistan

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Abstract:

The article is devoted to the study of the scientific heritage of Umarali Normatov, an outstanding Uzbek literary scholar and critic. The work analyzes the key factors that determined the formation of his scientific school in the university environment, and also examines the main achievements of the scientist in the field of literary criticism for more than sixty years of creative activity.

Keywords: Literary criticism, literary criticism, critic, National University of Uzbekistan, scientific environment, literary-critical thinking, recognition of teachers, activities of the scientist.

Introduction

In the last century the National of University after the named Mirzo Ulugbek one of the leading centers of literary and critical thinking of the Republic. Thanks to the efforts of literary scholars such as Gulom Karimov, Subutoy Dolimov, Ozod Sharafiddinov, Matyakub Koshjanov, Umarali Normatov, Sanjar Sadikov, Norboy Khudoyberganov, Abdugafur Rasulov, Begali Kasimov, a strong scientific school was formed in this place. Among them, Umarali Normatov, literary critic, critic, honored scientist, doctor of philology, professor, laureate of the Republican State Prize named after Hamza, winner of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, holder of the Order of “Labor

Fame” has a special place. Uzbek literary studies and criticism of the 20th century cannot be imagined without Umarali Normatov. As teacher Ozod Sharafiddinov said, “Talking about Umarali Normatov means talking about today's Uzbek criticism” [1]. Because Umarali Normatov's influence on the literary process as a scientist and critic, and his services in shaping the taste of the reader are extremely great. U. Normatov has a special place among critics such as I. Sultan, H. Yakubov, M. Koshjanov, N. Khudoyberganov in the achievements of modern criticism.

Literature analysis and methodology

The entire career of the teacher was spent at the National University of Uzbekistan. He became a student of the well-known literary critic O. Sharafiddinov, and studied the problems of artistic development of Uzbek storytelling under his guidance. He defended his candidate's thesis on the principles of development of Uzbek storytelling, and later his doctoral thesis. "The greatest wealth and happiness I found at the university is that I had the honor of being the first graduate student of Ozod Sharafiddinov. I consider it God's grace for me to work with him for half a century, to be his partner. Thanks to the creative courage of this person, the owner of unparalleled talent, our National University has become one of the centers of literary and critical thinking recognized by the modern scientific and literary community in our country” [2]. The incident of U. Normatov becoming an apprentice to O. Sharafiddinov dates back to 1959. The scientist defends his candidate's thesis on the topic "The main trends of the development of contemporary Uzbek storytelling" for the specified three years. He went through the scientific and pedagogical path from teacher to professor at the current National University. His mentor O. Sharafiddinov says: “First he became a teacher, then he worked as an associate professor. A few years ago, when the department of Uzbek Soviet literature was established, we all unanimously elected Umarali as the head of the department. In the meantime, he defended his doctoral dissertation and became a professor” [3]. U. Normatov headed the department for many years, he himself rose to the rank of teacher and supervised dozens of candidates of sciences and doctors. Umarali Normatov, as a worthy follower of the Ozod Sharafiddinov Scientific School, carried out extensive work. His students, such as D. Kuronov, H. Boltaboyev, B. Karimov, U. Hamdamov, who were mentored by the teacher, have reached the status of mentors. From 1957 until the end of his life, Umarali Normatov participated in the literary process with his literary-critical and scientific articles. “Genre possibilities”, “Secrets of skill” (in collaboration with M. Koshjanov), “Horizons of our prose”, “Meeting with beauty”, “Traditions of our prose”, “Said Akhamad”, “Fame”, “Talent training”, “Maturity”, “Light of mind and heart”, “Feeling of the times”, “Invulnerable world of the creator”, “The warm word of the creator” and other monographs and literary portraits are an important mark in the development of Uzbek literary criticism. Researches such as “Heart revolution”, “Qadiri park”, “The Wonder of Past Days” are among the serious achievements of modern Uzbek literary studies. The critic also paid attention to the identification of new literary and aesthetic principles that appeared in literature, and to researching the theoretical problems of the current literary flow. His books such as “Hopeful Principles”, “Tafakkur Yogdusi”, “The Magic of Creativity”, “The Last Plea of the Almighty”, “The Creator's Haro Ratli Sozi”, “Half-a-Century Shining Lighthouse”, published hundreds of literary works. he studied the same problems in his critical articles. U. Normatov's research and articles about the works of Abdulla Qadiri and Abdulla Qahhor have a special place in the literary process. Umarali Normatov is a leading creator who is constantly researching to enrich the diversity of genres of Uzbek criticism. His reviews, literary-critical articles, and literary conversations have a great place in our literary studies. In the second half of the 20th century, U. Normatov made a great contribution to the formation and

development of the genre of literary dialogue, becoming one of the leading genres in Uzbek criticism. Umarali Normatov is a critic who actively influenced the literary process and regularly observed it.

METHODS

Research Design

The study used the descriptive method. Descriptive research may be defined as a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, trends, and cause-effect relationships and then making adequate and accurate interpretations of such data with or without the aid of statistical methods (Calderon & Gonzales, 2014).

Research Locale

The study was conducted in selected Public Schools of the Division of San Jose del Monte City. The Division is located in the Southeastern part of Bulacan composed of ten (10) districts. District 1 has seven (7) schools followed by district 9 with six (6) while the rest have five (5) schools each. There was a total of 52 public schools divided into thirty-four (34) elementary and eighteen (18) high schools. In the listed 52 institutions, there were only eight (8) schools with a designated registrar securing plantilla. It includes Minuyan National High School, Kaypian National High School, Paradise Farms National High School, Graceville National High School, Muzon Harmony Hills National High School, Sapang Palay National High School, San Jose Del Monte National High School, and San Jose Del Monte National Trade School. The rest have no registrar, but the position is substituted either by administrative officer or designated teaching personnel as an ancillary function.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study comprised of the designated registrars of Schools with an established Registrar's Office which can be substituted by an Administrative Officer or Administrative Staff functioning as School Registrar or any teaching personnel performing an ancillary function as the school registrar. The School Head or Principals were also be counted as a respondent as the implementing group of Registrar's Office policies. Selected learners and the parents will respond to the stakeholders' group on the services rendered by the office. The respondents provided data that were beneficial in determining the effectiveness of technology-aided document management systems in institutions.

Sampling Technique

The research samples were classified into two groups including the implementing group involving the Registrars and School Heads while the second group is the stakeholder's group involving the learners and the parents. Since there was only one representation for the Registrar and the School Head or there was one assigned for every school, the sampling technique was not be applicable for this group. Whereas respondents from this group were the actual people to provide the data. However, in the stakeholders' group, purposive sampling was applied. Purposive sampling is determining the target population who will be involved in the study (Calderon & Gonzales, 2014).

The stakeholder group involving the learners and parents who get services from the registrar's office was chosen based on their knowledge of the information desired. To emphasize the purposiveness of the sampling, a representation of one (1) teaching personnel and one (1) student per school were applied to get an equal representation for each school or cluster. As a result, there will be a total of four (4) respondents from each school to provide the needed data for the study.

Research Instrument

The study used a survey questionnaire in conducting the research. The questionnaire used was grouped into the implementing group and the stakeholders' group with the same parts. Part 1 is consisted of the registrar's office functions or services rendered to the stakeholders including paperless transactions, record repository and archiving, communication to clients, and risk management. Part 2 is consisted of the characteristics of the technology-aided document or record management system of the registrar's office including confidentiality, integrity, availability, authenticity, control, and utilization. The questionnaire was composed of three (3) questions for every determinant of each variable to ensure the conciseness of the data provided where the instrument will be provided or administered to the respondents through an online form. On the other hand, a printed questionnaire was also provided depending on the respondent's convenience without compromising minimum health standards. Before disseminating the questionnaire, a validation process was conducted to assess the correctness of the questionnaire and ensured that each question corresponds to the needed data of the study. The validation was administered to local authorities in the Division Office to be able to obtain the best questionnaire validation results. A separate validation was also conducted on a teacher and parents randomly. To ensure reliability, the researcher attempted to attain a Cronbach Alpha between .71 to .95 which is the acceptable percentage to attain the most reliable and consistent data gathering instrument.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first wrote a letter to the City School Division of San Jose Del Monte City through the School Head of the researcher requesting to conduct the study. A validated questionnaire must also be presented before the approval of the research. Once approved, the researcher will secure a Division Memorandum from the Schools Division Superintendent, Assistant Schools Division Superintendent, and be honored by the Director of the Research Division. This process is a required procedure when conducting research within the division as part of the ethical standards, proper documentation, and future publication. Once a Division Memorandum is issued, the researcher started the distribution of the data gathering instrument. Questionnaires had disclosure of the privacy of the information provided by the respondents where the researcher informs the respondents that all responses shall be kept private, and secured and personal information is not compromised. After all the questionnaires were filled by the respondents, results were sorted, tallied, tabulated, and analyzed with the help of a statistician using a manual statistical computation method or with the aid of IBM SPSS Statistics Version 25 and above computer application.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Umarali Normatov is a critic who has researched various genres of Uzbek criticism. The works of the scientist in the genres of literary criticism, such as reviews, literary-critical articles, literary portraits, literary dialogues, and consistent monographic studies have undoubtedly enriched the treasure of our literary studies. The inquisitiveness of the critic shows that he boldly raises new problems of literature and that he strives to find ways and methods of interesting analysis of them. Critic Matyakub Koshjanov also gave positive comments about U. Normatov: “Umarali Normatov is now a critic”. He tries not to lose sight of a literary fact. He is a hard worker, his thoughts are strong, most of the time they are reasonable. His thoughts are vivid in expression” [3]. When U. Normatov studied modern Uzbek literature, he tried to approach it with the criteria of development principles of world literature. He always fought for the high level of fiction and literary criticism. criticized with A vivid example of this is the work “Encounter with Beauty” (1976). In the 80s of the 20th century, the desire to research the problems of the method and literary process in a scientific and large-scale manner increased. U. Normatov's books “Maturity” and “Revolution of the Heart” were published based on these requirements. Both of these books give an idea of the growing desire for innovation and generalizations in Uzbek criticism, the range of genres is expanding, the styles are becoming more diverse, and the level of specialization and skill of critics is increasing. Umarali Normatov led a group of authors on the creation of textbooks and study guides for general education schools on the basis of a radically renewed literary thinking, based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of March 1991. A new concept of literature teaching was developed under the guidance of a skilled pedagogue, and he participated as the author of textbooks and manuals for grades 5, 9, 11, leading a group of authors on creating programs and textbooks in accordance with it. The critic also showed his activity in the important field of creating textbooks and manuals for independent specialists that can meet the requirements of the new system in all subjects, especially social and humanitarian areas. U. Normatov created the textbook “Uzbek literature of the 20th century” for the 11th grades in co-authorship with N. Karimov and B. Nazarov. In the textbook, the works of the great figures of the national renaissance were interpreted in the spirit of the ideas of independence. Also, one of the authors of the textbook created for the 9th grade is U. Normatov. The textbook “History of 20th century Uzbek literature” written for students of universities and pedagogical institutes was created in cooperation with O. Sharafiddinov, N. Karimov, S. Mamajonov, B. Nazarov and U. Normatov. The textbook “New Uzbek literature” was published. U. Normatov's articles about literature in a new spirit and its development, modernism, became a necessary resource for young critics.

Discussion

“Where did you study and where did you work?” My answer to these questions is only one - I received my higher and post-graduate education at the prestigious institution, which is now called the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek. I spent almost sixty years of my life at this institution. “I got the title of laureate of the state award because of my services here” [4], he says. U. Normatov was recognized by his teachers even when he was a university student. The scientist was known as an accomplished specialist in modern Uzbek literature, in particular, Uzbek novels. Doctor of philological sciences, professor Umarali Normatov was recognized not only by our country, but also by higher educational institutions and scientific centers in the field of philology of the Central Asian countries as a passionate teacher, a well-known literary scholar. Literary and critical works of the literary scholar are devoted to issues of the modern literary process and the history and development of new Uzbek literature. His analysis of rare works of our national literature, the unique features of new Uzbek literature, and scientific and theoretical works on the principles of development

have been recognized by the literary community. For his literary and critical articles, he received awards from the magazines “Eastern Star”, “Tafakkur”, “Guliston”. Through the book “Miracle of Power”, the reader feels the warmth of the scientist's heart, witnesses exciting literary and scientific analyzes full of pleasure. Of course, the scientist did not write this book in one or two years or in one sitting. Studying and researching all aspects of Abdulla Qadiri's life and work, scientific works related to the writer, is a long and hard work. Umarali Normatov was engaged in this work throughout his life. When it came time, he wrote down his research and observations. The number of articles published by U. Normatov in periodical press is more than five hundred, and the number of separately published books is more than twenty. In 2010, Umarali Normatov published two books of different quality. One is called "Grunts of Refinement," which includes six sections of literary criticism, essays, memoirs, notes, and interviews, many of which are being referred to readers for the first time. It is surprising that there are many unpublished works in the creative chest of the teacher. By reading the articles in the first chapters of the book called “The example of the teachers” and “In the circle of the rank-and-file”, one can notice another characteristic of Umarali Normatov's image. This is the sense of discipleship and friendship of a teacher with high spirituality and firm faith. As he admits, the greatest wealth and happiness he gained while studying at the university was the fact that he was a student of a great teacher like Azod Sharafiddinov. Thanks to Azod Sharafiddinov, he was lucky enough to have an interview with Abdulla Qahhor. At the same time, as a student of the teacher, teachers and colleagues such as “Ustozi avval”, Gulom Karimov, “Adamakhun Siymo”, “Subutoy Dolimov”, “East-West researcher”, Fazila Sulaymanova, “Scientist, translator, coach”, Shoislom Shomuhamedov, colleagues and friends Nuriddin Shukurov, Begali Kasimov, Norboy Khudoyberganov, Abdugafur Rasulov also tell stories with sincerity and love. For this reason, Umarali Normatov first of all bows to these teachers for whatever career and prestige he has achieved. Perhaps, that is why Umarali Normatov himself has been highly loved by his students.

Summary

Umarali Normatov was an inquisitive critic. “A critic is a special talent. A critic is a creator. A writer goes through life to a book. A critic comes to life through a book. He opens the books. Always open to discovery in this sense. A teacher needs erudition like water and air. But a critic cannot be imagined without erudition. A critic will be matured only when erudition is matured” [5] said the artist of Uzbekistan, literary critic Ibrahim Gafurov. There is an article entitled "Poet of Linguistics" by teacher Umarali Normatov about the linguist Ayyub Ghulomov in the 2014 number 2 of “East Star” magazine. In this article, teacher A. Ghulomov remembers: "In the end, I used to think that this handsome, fair, neat, well-groomed, healthy breed with a radiant face would live for a hundred years. It didn't happen. All his life, scientific-pedagogical activity was under the pressure, turmoil, ideological-political pressure of this unique scientist, he swallowed his original interests, dreams, pains and sorrows, and did not reveal them even to his closest friends, until he reached the age of 70. suddenly drowned, had a serious heart disease, died at the age of 72. "As soon as our teacher left us, there was an irreparable loss in my life, university, neighborhood, linguistics, etc." It is regrettable to say that after the death of Umarali Normatov, our literary studies department, there was a huge loss and loss in the life of our university, literature and our students.

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